

Stable cycling of halide solid state electrolyte enabled by a dynamic layered solid electrolyte interphase between Li metal and $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_4\text{Br}_2$

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ABSTRACT

Halides are potential electrolytes for Li metal solid state batteries owing to their combination of high ionic conductivity, ductility and electrochemical stability against oxidation. However, their reactivity with the Li metal electrode may result in the formation of secondary compounds hindering their practical utility in terms of cycling performance as key indicator in battery operation. In this work, we investigate the high performance of symmetric cells with $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_4\text{Br}_2$ halide and bare Li-metal electrode, able to withstand 1000 h of Li electrodeposition-dissolution with an overpotential as low as 46 mV. Through a comprehensive analysis employing physico-chemical and electrochemical characterizations, complemented by computational methodologies, we unravel the dynamics of the complex of the Li/halide interface and its evolution during cycling. The reactivity between $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_4\text{Br}_2$ with metallic Li results in the reduction of the halide into LiCl, LiBr and Y metal. Surprisingly, during cycling, those secondary products from the reduction of the halide build a structured solid electrolyte interphase, containing a Y-rich electronic conductive and LiCl and LiBr ionic conductive layers. The particular chemistry and robustness of this solid electrolyte interphase exhibiting a mixed ionic and electronic conductivity appears to be responsible for the outstanding cycling stability.

1. Introduction

In recent years, halide materials have emerged as compelling solid electrolytes for Li-ion batteries, positioning themselves as leading contenders alongside polymers, oxides, and sulfides due to their appealing properties [1–4]. Initially overlooked for this application, early studies on chloroaluminates like LiAlCl_4 , NaAlCl_4 , and KAlCl_4 revealed discouragingly low ionic conductivities ranging from 10^{-6} to 10^{-9} S cm^{-1} at 25 °C [5]. However, recent advancements, such as those reported by Asano et al. [6], have showcased promising results with materials like Li_3YCl_6 (LYC) and Li_3YBr_6 (LYB) prepared by mechanosynthesis displaying high conductivities nearing 1 mS cm^{-1} at 25 °C. Since then, significant progress has been made in developing halide materials, especially focusing on structures like monoclinic and trigonal metal compounds Li_3MX_6 ($M = \text{Sc}, \text{Y}, \text{In}, \text{Hf}, \text{Ho}, \text{Er}, \text{Yb}$ and $X =$

$\text{F}, \text{Cl}, \text{Br}$ and I), as well as cubic chlorospinel [7].

Halides exhibit superior ionic conductivity compared to oxides and polymer electrolytes, with oxyhalides like LiNbOCl_4 and LiTaOCl_4 even surpassing that of common sulfides [3]. Beyond their high ionic conductivity, halides feature a broader electrochemical redox potential range than oxides and sulfides, rendering them better suited for use with high-voltage cathode materials [6–9]. Through the strategic chemical design of halogen stoichiometry on the halide composition, employing a dual-halogen approach, electrochemical features can be improved compared to single halogen compounds [10]. For example, while LYB displays higher ionic conductivity than LYC, it has a lower oxidation potential limit. By incorporating Cl and Br to synthesize compounds like $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_{4.5}\text{Br}_{1.5}$, it becomes feasible to attain superior ionic conductivity compared to LYC as well as an additional 0.5 V higher oxidation potential limit than LYB [11], thus establishing the dual Cl-Br halide family

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as a promising electrolyte option. Furthermore, halides possess high ductility [12], unlike oxides, making them ideal candidates for scaling up stacking and densification steps in cell manufacturing.

The primary obstacle hampering the incorporation of halide materials into solid-state Li-ion batteries lies in their stability toward the Li metal electrode [1], which is the most promising anode for this technology as it has the highest theoretical specific capacity. Having a low reduction potential, halides are reduced upon contact with lithium even without applying any galvanostatic current. Fu et al. [13] and Riegger et al. [14] have demonstrated through X-ray diffraction (XRD) and X-ray photoelectron spectroscopy (XPS) the reduction of Li_3MX_6 by Li into LiX and M^0 . Thus, the reduction of halides by Li results in the formation of an interphase characterized by mixed ionic and electronic conduction. Such interphase formation suggests continuous reduction [15], expected to cease only upon complete consumption of either the halide or the Li electrode, thereby limiting battery lifespan. While some studies report an increase of the overpotential during symmetric cells stripping/plating (ST/PT) due to this reactivity [16–21], other halides present a stable overpotential after some cycling [22–24], suggesting a stabilization of the interface that remains to be fully understood.

Researchers are currently focused on enhancing the Li/halide interface, primarily aiming to achieve a stable Solid Electrolyte Interphase (SEI) to prevent further electrolyte degradation. A deep understanding of the interface dynamics is therefore key for this endeavor. Various pathways have been explored to address this challenge. One approach involves substituting the bare Li anode with an In-Li alloy. Thermodynamic equilibrium voltage calculations reveal that while the reduction potential of LYC and LYB is around 0.6 V vs Li/Li⁺ [25], the use of an In-Li alloy electrode demonstrates an improvement with the lower redox potential (0.62 V vs Li/Li⁺) [26]. A 50 at% of In is needed as lower content leads to a reduced redox potential, rendering it thermodynamically unstable. Despite its potential, utilizing an In-based anode presents some drawbacks: (i) it diminishes the cell voltage by 0.6 V, thus jeopardizing the energy density; and (ii) the high cost of In precludes its viability for industry. Another way to improve the Li/halide interface is the introduction of an interlayer to protect the halide from direct contact with the Li electrode [27]. Sulfide materials such as $\text{Li}_6\text{PS}_5\text{Cl}$ argyrodite [16,21,28–31], Li_3PS_4 [9,32], $\text{Li}_{6.7}\text{Si}_{0.7}\text{Sb}_{0.3}\text{S}_5\text{I}$ [7,32], or $\text{Li}_{12}\text{GeP}_2\text{S}_{12}$ [33] have been widely used owed to their ability to form insulating species such as Li_2S , Li_3P , or LiCl , which are beneficial for the interface stabilization [34,35]. Yet, careful attention must be given to the choice of the halide, as not all are inert toward the argyrodite. This is the case of Li_3InCl_6 , for which the reaction with argyrodite leads to the formation of an InS-like compound, confirmed by ToF-SIMS imaging, leading to a drastic increase of the impedance and a fast capacity fading during cycling [36]. The vast majority of work on halide full cells apply either In anode [18,23], In-Li alloy anode [6,24], sulfide interlayer [21,30,31], or the association of In or In-Li alloy anode with an interlayer [7,9,16,28,29,32,33,37], reporting a high capacity retention upon cycling (80–95 % retention over 100–200 cycles).

To improve the cycling performance of halides with bare Li electrodes, the *in situ* formation of a SEI or a protective layer is of interest. As such, recent studies use the modification of the composition by incorporating a small fraction of F to replace Cl and Br atoms [17,19,20,38,39]. Fluorinated halides increase the electrochemical stability toward oxidation, although the high electronegativity of F^- anions decreases the ionic conductivity with respect to their analogous with Cl and Br [3]. Like the other halides, fluorinated halides also react with Li metal resulting in the formation of LiF. LiF is well known to promote the uniform deposition of Li metal, thus being a desirable component in the SEI. The dynamic formation of a LiF-containing SEI has been confirmed during the cycling of halides in symmetric cells with bare Li electrodes. Consequently, fluorinated halides display a more stable ST/PT cycling compared to their derivatives without F as well as a better capacity retention of full cells with Li or In-Li alloy anodes. Zhang et al. [40] report the *in situ* formation of a protective layer in liquid cells by mixing

Li_3InCl_6 (LIC) with a conventional electrolyte such as LiPF_6 . The authors describe the formation of a homogeneous SEI composed of LIC, LiCl and Li_xIn_y , In^0 (obtained after reduction of LIC by Li) alloying with Li. This SEI, inhibits the propagation of dendrites, thereby improving the voltage profile during ST/PT and enhancing the cycling performance of liquid full cells. However, this LIC-based SEI has not been observed in solid-state cells, as reports primarily describe LIC-based full cells using In or In-Li alloy anodes with a sulfide interlayer [30,33,41,42].

A deep understanding of the Li/halide interface is of importance to provide guidelines on the design of stable SEI enabling high anode performance, which represents the best approach to the use of bare Li electrodes on full-cell solid state batteries. In this work, we unravel the dynamics of the interface between halide and Li metal electrodes. The materials from the family Li_3MX_6 [2] present higher ionic conductivity than spinel halides. Furthermore Y-based halides are among the most investigated, however, there is no report about their interaction with Li metal upon cycling. The formation of a LiF-based protective layer has been demonstrated but the presence of F leads to a decrease of the ionic conductivity [19,38], which might inhibit the performances under strong conditions. On the other hand, the system $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_{6-x}\text{Br}_x$ is well known to present improved ionic conductivity compared to their single-halogen equivalents [10,11], however the properties of its interface with Li upon cycling have not yet been investigated. As such, our interest was focused on this system and more particularly on the mixed Cl-Br halide $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_4\text{Br}_2$ (LYCB). Employing a combination of computational modelling and experiments, we elucidated the reactive nature of LYCB with Li metal, resulting in the formation of ionic and electronic conductive species. Through postmortem analysis, we observe the evolution of the interface, which transforms into a robust SEI created during the initial cycling stage. The chemistry of this dynamic SEI contributes to the thermodynamic stability with Li metal. In addition, this interface enhances the electrodeposition and dissolution of Li during cycling. The symmetric cells withstand over 1000 h of cycling at a capacity and a current density of 0.5 mAh cm⁻² and 0.1 mA cm⁻², respectively, without propagation of Li dendrites. This work highlights the significance of the rational design and engineering of a robust SEI that might pave the way for building high-performance solid-state batteries with halide electrolyte and bare Li electrodes.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Materials

All the materials have been carried out in a glove box under Ar atmosphere ($\text{H}_2\text{O} \leq 0.1$ ppm and $\text{O}_2 \leq 0.1$ ppm). In this study, the LYCB powder was supplied by Saint-Gobain. Similar $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_{6-x}\text{Br}_x$ compounds have been synthesized according to methods described in recent literature [4,10,11]. Li metal has been purchased from China Energy Lithium Co., Ltd in the form of 500 μm chips.

2.2. Characterizations

XRD was conducted on solid electrolytes using a Bruker D8 Discover X-ray diffractometer with $\lambda_{\text{Cu,K}\alpha 1} = 1.54056$ Å, in the range of $2\theta = 10$ – 80° and a step-size of 0.02° . All samples were mounted onto an atmosphere protective XRD sample holder with a Kapton film cover in order to avoid atmospheric moisture contact. The morphology of the halides at the surface of the samples were assessed via Scanning Electron Microscopy (SEM) using a QUANTA200 from Thermofisher. Magic Angle Spinning Nuclear Magnetic Resonance (MAS-NMR) spectroscopy was performed on pristine halide powder and halide powder obtained after ST/PT using a Bruker Avance III 500 MHz spectrometer equipped with a 2.5 mm probe. The MAS frequency was set to 20 kHz. ^7Li 1D experiment were performed using single excitation pulses (2.4 μs) and relaxation delays of 1200s to ensure full relaxation of the nuclei.

Fig. 1. Physico-Chemical characterizations and ionic conductivity measurements of LYCB. (a) SEM micrography. (b) XRD pattern (the main peaks are indexed). (c) ^7Li MAS-NMR spectrum. (d) Arrhenius plot of the ionic conductivity.

2.3. Symmetric cell preparation

LYCB was compacted into pellets for electrochemical characterizations. 75 mg of powder were loaded into a 6 mm diameter die and pressed at 4 t cm^{-2} (390 MPa) for 1 min. The thickness of the resulting pellets was 1 ± 0.1 mm. Symmetric cells with carbon coated on aluminium (C-Al) blocking electrodes were assembled to obtain the ionic and electronic conductivity. ST/PT cycling was performed on symmetric cells with lithium electrodes of $150 \mu\text{m}$ thickness, obtained after laminating the Li chip.

2.4. Electrochemical characterizations

All electrochemical tests were performed in air-tight home-made cells (Swagelok type) without external pressure applied during the measurements. For the temperature-dependent ionic conductivity, Electrochemical Impedance Spectroscopy (EIS) was recorded at 25°C and every 10°C from 30 to 80°C , using a Solartron 1260A Frequency Response Analyzer module from 32 MHz to 1 Hz with a bias voltage of 20 mV . It was also used to evaluate the interfacial stability of LYCB with lithium electrodes. The electronic conductivity was obtained from chronoamperometric (CA) measurements every 0.05 V between 0.2 and 0.4 V for 1 h at each potential, with a VMP3 potentiostat from Biologic. ST/PT cycling was performed at a constant capacity of 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} and a constant current density of 0.1 mA cm^{-2} for 100 cycles with a Series 4000 MACCOR battery tester.

2.5. Post-mortem analysis

In order to carry out an analytical study and to obtain a spatial distribution of the elements in the samples, the Li/halide interface after cycling was analyzed by field emission scanning electron microscopy (FE-SEM) combined with the elemental detection given by the windowless-EDX in an APREO microscope from the Thermofisher company. A sharp cross section was obtained by ion milling on a IM4000 PLUS from HITACHI. Thanks to these capabilities, besides the sealed sample transfer system for protecting the samples from the environmental conditions during its transportation from the glove box and the FE-SEM, elemental mappings were obtained on the samples cross sections. For post cycling XRD and NMR analysis, lithium electrodes were removed from the symmetric cells and the surface of the pellet was polished, prior crushing into powder.

2.6. Computational methods

In addition, to elucidate the mechanism of SEI formation at the atomic level, we performed a computational study using Li/LYCB interface models. The calculations included the following key steps: (i) exploring the configuration space of disordered structure of LYCB; (ii) building Li/LYCB interface models using a lattice matching algorithm [[43]], (iii) performing *ab initio* molecular dynamics (AIMD) simulations of the interface models, and (iv) conducting Bader charge analysis of the resultant AIMD trajectories to monitor the charge transfer events among various species during interfacial reaction.

The exploration of the configuration space was carried out using the Supercell program [44]. To avoid exceeding the unit cell size feasible for

Fig. 2. Stability of LYCB with Li electrodes. (a) Nyquist plots of a Li/LYCB/Li cell at various intervals of time after assembly. (b) Evolution of the bulk, interfacial, and total resistances of the Li/LYCB/Li cell with time; the total resistance corresponds to the sum of the bulk and the interfacial resistances. (c) Picture of a LYCB pellet before and after being in contact with Li metal for eight days.

the AIMD simulations, we slightly adjusted the site occupancies of the experimentally determined LYCB structure (Table S1). In total, we performed geometry optimization and energy calculations for 168 symmetrically unique LYCB configurations. The lowest energy configuration, together with the metal Li structure from the Materials Project database [45] was used to construct three Li(110)/LYCB(110), Li(100)/LYCB(211), and Li(010)/LYCB(210) interface models (Fig. S1). The numbers in parentheses denote the crystallographic directions of Li and LYCB planes at the interface. To build these models, we enumerated all possible symmetrically nonequivalent crystallographic directions with Miller indices in range from -3 to 3 . However, to ensure the models are computationally feasible for DFT calculations, we used a restriction on the maximum surface area of 400 \AA^2 across the interface. The geometry of each model was then geometrically optimized before using them as starting structures for the AIMD simulations.

The AIMD simulations relied on underlying density functional theory (DFT) calculations and were carried out using the Vienna ab initio simulation package (VASP) version 5.4 [46–48], employing the Perdew–Burke–Ernzerhof (PBE) [49] exchange–correlation functional and PBE-based projector augmented wave potentials [50,51]. A 600 eV

energy cutoff parameter was used. The calculations of bulk structures and interface models were performed using a Monkhorst-Pack Brillouin zone sampling [52] with a Γ -centered $2 \times 1 \times 2$ and Γ -only k-point mesh, respectively. The geometry optimization employed a force convergence parameter of 0.05 eV/\AA . AIMD simulations were carried out in the NVT ensemble at 298 K. The time step of 1 fs and Nose–Hoover thermostat [53] with a Nose-mass parameter of 0.5 were used. The Bader atomic charges were calculated using the Bader code implemented by Tang et al. [54].

3. Results and discussion

SEM micrograph analysis (Fig. 1a), reveals that LYCB powder consists of polyhedron-shaped particles with non-uniform size ranging from 50 nm to a few μm . The X-ray diffractogram of the LYCB in Fig. 1b confirms the crystalline structure of LYCB, with all peaks indexed to the halide electrolyte. LYCB crystallizes within the $C2/m$ space group, similarly to the Li_3ErBr_6 halide (ICSD No 50,182) and to $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_3\text{Br}_3$ and $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_{1.5}\text{Br}_{4.5}$ [11]. The LYCB cell parameters obtained after refinement (Fig. S2 and Table S2) are $a = 6.6994(3) \text{ \AA}$, $b = 11.5899(4) \text{ \AA}$, $c = 6.6263$

Fig. 3. Cycling properties of LYCB. (a) ST/PT of Li/LYCB/Li cell at a capacity of 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} and a current density of 0.1 mA cm^{-2} . Regions A, B and C characterize the increase, decrease and stabilization of the overpotential, respectively. Inset is a zoom on the profile of the 2nd and 3rd cycles. (b) Nyquist plots recorded at the OCV after different stages of ST/PT. (c) Evolution of the bulk, interfacial and total resistances, and of the electronic conductivity after various cycles.

Fig. 4. Computational study. (a) The final frame of the 100 ps AIMD simulations. Black circles highlight completely reduced Y atoms. (b) Evolution of Y-Cl and Li-Cl coordination numbers along the AIMD trajectories. (c) Evolution of average atomic charges along the AIMD trajectories, with guiding lines aiding visualization.

(2) Å, and $\beta = 109.977(1)^\circ$, leading to a crystallographic density of 2.83 g cm^{-3} . These cell parameters are smaller than those reported for Li_3ErBr_6 , which can be explained by the presence of Cl^- , with a smaller ionic radius than Br^- (1.81 vs 1.96 Å), while Y^{3+} and Er^{3+} possess similar ionic radius (0.9 and 0.89 Å, respectively). The ^7Li NMR spectrum of LYCB (Fig. 1c) consists of a single narrow signal centered at -0.35 ppm suggesting the presence of Li^+ with high mobility. In Li_3MX_6 halides, Li^+ are present in two positions and might display different mobilities as demonstrated by Yu et al. [18] using AIMD simulations. As such, the ^7Li NMR spectrum may include two signals with different linewidths that may appear overlapped at a similar chemical shift.

The Nyquist plots, along with corresponding ionic conductivities recorded at various temperatures for a LYCB pellet are represented in Fig. S3 and 1d, respectively. At lower temperatures, the Nyquist plots exhibit one semi-circle in the high frequency range, attributed to the bulk resistance of the halide. As temperature increases, this semi-circle gradually diminishes, eventually becoming imperceptible at higher temperatures. The ionic conductivity of LYCB at 25°C is 1.8 mS cm^{-1} , which increases up to 10 mS cm^{-1} at 80°C . The resulting activation energy, measured at 0.28 eV, positions LYCB among the most rapid Li^+ conductors within the LiMX_6 halide family. The electronic conductivity of LYCB measured by chronoamperometry is $2.6 \cdot 10^{-9} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$ (Fig. S4), i. e., six orders of magnitude lower than its ionic conductivity, confirming its insulating nature, similar to other solid electrolytes [55].

Halides are well known to undergo interfacial chemical instability with Li metal [13,14], leading to the formation of resistive LiX ($X = \text{Cl}, \text{Br}, \text{F}$) species, increasing the overall cell resistance, thereby hampering their use as solid electrolytes. As such, understanding the chemistry and dynamics of the interface between halide and Li metal is necessary to design interlayers ensuring sufficient contact, efficient carrier transport, and dendrite suppression, which are key for a stable cell performance. To evaluate the stability of LYCB with Li metal, EIS measurements were conducted on a symmetric Li/LYCB/Li cell at various intervals over eight days (Fig. 2a). The EIS parameters and the equivalent circuit used for fitting the spectra are reported in Fig. S5 and Table S3. The Nyquist plots display two distinct semi-circles: one in the high frequency range (16 MHz - 400 kHz), attributed to the bulk resistance (R_b), and another in the medium-low frequency range (400 kHz - 1 Hz), ascribed to the interfacial resistance between LYCB and Li metal (R_{int}). The evolution of R_b , R_{int} , and the total resistance (R_{tot} , sum of bulk and interfacial resistances) is reported in Fig. 2b. An asymptotic trend with a rapid resistance increase is observed for the Li/LYCB/Li cell after being in contact during 8 days. Detailed analysis reveals that R_b increases by 140 % over the eight-day period, a significantly smaller change compared to R_{int} (450 %). Overall, R_{tot} increased by 310 % within eight days. The relevant increase of R_{int} confirms the reactivity between LYCB and Li electrodes. Simultaneously, the increase of R_b indicates that such reactivity leads to the formation of secondary products, exacerbating the decrease in LYCB's ionic conductivity. This reduction in LYCB's ionic conductivity might be attributed to the formation of a SEI comprising less conductive species upon contact with Li metal. The observed blackening of the pellet surface area in contact with Li metal (Fig. 2c) further corroborates the halide's reactivity toward Li metal.

To assess the impact of the Li metal interfacial reactivity on the cycling properties, ST/PT has been performed on a symmetric cell over 100 cycles (0.5 mAh cm^{-2} ; 0.1 mA cm^{-2}) as displayed in Fig. 3a. The evolution of the overpotential during the ST/PT unveils three distinct regions. Initially (region A), spanning the first 15 cycles, the overpotential steadily increases to a maximum of 270 mV. A closer look into each step (inset Fig. 3a) reveals an incremental cell polarization during both the electroplating and dissolution processes. Subsequently (region B), there is a gradual decrease of the overpotential until it stabilizes after 30 cycles (equivalent to 300 h of cycling). Finally, region C shows a flat voltage profile maintaining a stable cycling. After 1000 h of cycling, the symmetric cell displays an outstanding overpotential as low as 46 mV. The initial increase in overpotential during region A is likely attributed

to the reactivity between LYCB and Li metal, as evidenced by EIS. Despite the increasing cell resistance, the LYCB/Li interface unexpectedly appears to improve over time, favoring prolonged cycling. Previous works on halide electrolytes have shown a continual increase in overpotential due to reactivity with Li metal [16,18–21]. However, fluorinated halides may stabilize the interface by forming a protective LiF-based SEI [19,20]. Notably, a similar behavior to LYCB during ST/PT has also been observed in other halides such as $\text{Li}_3\text{HoCl}_4\text{Br}_2$ [22], $\text{Li}_{2.73}\text{Ho}_{1.09}\text{Cl}_6$ [24], $\text{Li}_3\text{YBr}_{5.7}\text{F}_{0.3}$ [17], and Li_3ScCl_6 [23], however an experimental confirmation of a favourable modification of the interface has not been demonstrated. Except for the latter, the overpotential remains within the same order of magnitude, approximately 50 mV.

To elucidate the outstanding performance of LYCB and the dynamics of the interface, several techniques were applied to observe the evolution of LYCB during cycling. First, the Nyquist plot at different stages of ST/PT were measured (Fig. 3b) and the evolution of R_b , R_{int} , and R_{tot} during cycling is reported in Fig. 3c. The EIS parameters and the equivalent circuit used for fitting the spectra are reported in Fig. S5 and Table S4. One can notice that during the 15 first cycles (region A), both R_b and R_{int} increase due to the reactivity between Li and LYCB, with the higher R_b leading to a decrease of the ionic conductivity. Another sign of reactivity is the rise of the electronic conductivity during the same period (Fig. 3c), with a two order of magnitude increase ($5.8 \cdot 10^{-7} \text{ S cm}^{-1}$). This suggests the formation of a SEI comprising secondary products, lowering the ionic conductivity while enhancing the electronic one. As the overpotential progresses (regions B and C), both R_b and the electronic conductivity remain constant, suggesting the stabilization of the interface between Li and LYCB. However, after 15 cycles, R_{int} drops by a factor of 2 (962 vs 426 $\Omega \text{ cm}^2$ after 15 and 100 cycles, respectively). Such decrease is likely due to an improvement of the contact between the solid electrolyte and the Li electrodes [17], promoted by the stable SEI already built during cycling. Further analysis of the LYCB/Li interface is necessary to understand this phenomenon, which is beneficial for cycling.

To deepen our understanding of the atomic-scale evolution of the Li/LYCB interface, we conducted a series of computational simulations. Specifically, we employed AIMD to explore the behavior of the Li/LYCB interface, as illustrated in Fig. S1. The geometry optimization of the interface models results in insignificant structural changes, except for the $\text{Li}(100)/\text{LYCB}(211)$ model (Fig. S6). In this case the breaking of some Y-Cl bonds at the interface is observed, accompanied by a transformation of octahedral coordination environments of some Y atoms into square pyramids. The AIMD simulations of these interface models reveal electrolyte degradation, indicated by a continuous decrease in the system's potential energy over time (Fig. S7). The degradation mechanism involves the breaking of Y-Cl(Br) bonds and the formation of new Li-Cl(Br) contacts (Fig. 4a). As follows from the evolution of coordination numbers (Fig. 4b), the $\text{Li}(110)/\text{LYCB}(110)$ interface model exhibits the highest reaction rate among the others. Bader charge analysis further demonstrates electron transfer between the Li anode and LYCB (Fig. 4c). As the Li metal charges increase, the average charges of Y decrease, while the anion charges remain constant. Although fluctuations in the Y charges may arise from performing Bader analysis for a nonequilibrium geometry, the overall trend is evident. Similar fluctuations in Li charges within LYCB, unrelated to redox reactions, are also observed. Based on these findings, we can conclude that Li reduces the halide electrolyte, yielding metal Y, LiCl, and LiBr as reaction products. While 100 ps of simulation may not be sufficient to observe the formation of these phases, intermediate products are detectable in the initial stages of the reaction. Towards the end of the AIMD trajectories, partially and fully reduced Y atoms are present, with the latter notably concentrated on the Li slab (see Fig. 4a). A similar reaction mechanism was observed in a previous AIMD simulation, which noted a concentration of reduced Y at the Li slab of the $\text{Li/Li}_3\text{YCl}_6$ solid electrolyte interface [56]. The preferential formation of metal Y at the interface with the Li anode, along with LiCl and LiBr at the interface with the electrolyte, can be

Fig. 5. Evolution of LYCB during Li/LYCB/Li ST/PT cycling at a capacity of 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} and a current density of 0.1 mA cm^{-2} . (a) ^7Li NMR spectra of LYCB powder after 15 and 50 cycles. Insets on top left are ^7Li NMR spectra of LYCB powder after 15 and 50 cycles at the chemical shift of Li metal. (b) X-ray diffractogram of LYCB powder after 100 cycles.

anticipated. This spatial distribution of reaction products may facilitate the formation of a stable interface that could protect the electrolyte from further degradation.

We further conducted ^7Li solid state NMR spectroscopy on LYCB after 15 and 50 cycles, aiming to delve deeper into the chemical structure dynamics during cycling and corroborate the computational insights (Fig. 5a). Notably, a significant broadening of the Li signal linewidth is observed for LYCB after 15 and 50 cycles. The Li signals are deconvoluted into three contributions for both samples. One signal, centered at -0.65 ppm with a linewidth of 18 Hz, was also present in the pristine and is attributed to Li occupying a specific position within LYCB. However, the other two components exhibit broader linewidths of 205 and 1149 Hz, respectively, indicating the formation of new phases during cycling as side products of the reaction between LYCB and Li. Interestingly, the ratio of these phases increases with prolonged cycling. And the broad linewidth of these new phases indicates a sluggish ionic transport compared to pristine LYCB. Liang et al. [24] suggested that the decrease of the overpotential during ST/PT might be attributed to the increase of the electroactive surface area of Li electrodes due to dendrite growth in the grain boundaries of the solid electrolyte. However, our examination on the chemical shift range around 260 and 270 ppm characteristic of Li metal (inset Fig. 5a) reveals the absence of a signal after 15 and 50 cycles, confirming the absence of Li dendrites in LYCB after cycling. This finding highlights the complex nature of the phenomena occurring at the Li/LYCB interface during cycling.

Additionally, XRD on LYCB after 100 cycles (Fig. 5b) confirms the reactivity of LYCB with Li during cycling. The diffractogram shows the presence of LYCB peaks in addition to LiCl and LiBr. LiCl and LiBr are

known to be poor Li-ion conductors, which is in good agreement with the broader signals observed on the NMR, the increase of R_B after cycling (Fig. 3a-b, region A), as well as the results of the AIMD simulations. Furthermore, Y metal is also detected on the diffractogram. The presence of Y as product of the reaction between LYCB and Li contributes to the increase of the electronic conductivity during the early stage of the cycling. Notably, the presence of Y, LiBr, and LiCl has also been reported for LYC and LYB at the interface with Li metal by Fu et al. [13]. Specifically, the following oxido-reduction reaction was proposed: $\text{Li}_3\text{YCl}_4\text{Br}_2 + 3 \text{Li} \rightarrow 4 \text{LiCl} + 2 \text{LiBr} + \text{Y}$, which means that the interphase formed at the solid electrolyte/Li interface is a mixed ionic/electronic conductor (MIEC). A MIEC interface is not beneficial for solid state batteries, as it provides both Li ions and electrons necessary for the reduction of the solid electrolyte [15]. Thus, a continuous reduction reaction of the solid electrolyte is to be expected until the total consumption of either the halide electrolyte or the Li electrode. This would be characterized by a continuous increase of R_B and the electronic conductivity, but also of the interfacial resistance, which is not the case for the LYCB halide. It has been shown that after an initial reduction reaction of LYCB by Li, the LYCB/Li interface has become stable, allowing a long cycling of the Li/LYCB/Li symmetric cell.

We analyzed the microstructural composition of the LYCB/Li interface by SEM/EDX from a sharp ion-milled cross section after 100 cycles (Fig. 6). Oxygen was detected by EDX through the entire linear mapping. For a better view of the EDX profile, the oxygen atomic percentage has been removed on Fig. 6e. Four distinct layers can be clearly distinguished. The top layer, labelled L1, contains all the elements and results from the ion-milling process as the pulverized elements are re-deposited

Fig. 6. SEM/EDX analysis of the LYCB/Li interface after 100 ST/PT cycles ($0.5 \text{ mAh cm}^{-2} / 0.1 \text{ mA cm}^{-2}$). (a) SEM micrography of the interface. Four layers can be identified: L1 is a contamination layer, L2 is the Li electrode, L3 is a Y-rich interlayer and L4 is the LYCB electrolyte. (b), (c) and (d) Cl K, Br L and Y L mapping, respectively, of the area represented in 6a. (e) Linear mapping of Li K, Cl K, Br L and Y L corresponding to the yellow arrow in 6a. Oxygen was also profiled during the EDX linear mapping, for a clearer view, its atomic percentage has been removed from (e).

on the sample. The layer below (L2) corresponds to the Li metal electrode. Layer L4 corresponds to LYCB, with a homogenous distribution of Y, Cl, and Br across the pellet thickness, whose atomic percentages match with the stoichiometry of Y, Cl and Br in LYCB. Lastly, an inter-layer (L3) is observed between the Li electrode and LYCB. According to the EDX mapping, including the linear in Fig. 6e, Cl and Br are present, with Y being the predominant element. As a reminder, 100 ps of AIMD

simulation reveals the penetration of Y atoms (obtained after reduction of LYCB) towards the Li electrode, which after a 1000 h cycling, appears to accumulate into an approximately $10 \mu\text{m}$ layer. Furthermore, along the side of the LYCB pellet (L4), a well-shaped drop in the Y content is observed, while Cl and Br levels increase above the expected atomic percentages corresponding to the stoichiometric LYCB. This might coincide with an area rich in LiCl and LiBr (products of the reactivity

Fig. 7. Formation of the Ionic-Electronic Layered Interface (IELI) during Li/LYCB/Li cycling.

between Li and LYCB), electronic insulator, in which Y diffused towards the Li electrode, making L3. This complex interface is characterized as a structured ionic-electronic layered interface (IELI). It appears that the formation of the IELI initiates only after 15 cycles, once the overpotential begins to decrease. Indeed, the SEM/EDX analysis has been performed at the interface of a cell after only 5 cycles (Fig. S8), and such a Y-rich interlayer is not present. Lu et al. [29] suggest that the products issued from the reduction of the halide by Li would be inserted in the micro-voids present at the interface and then will diffuse to create a layer which then will protect the electrolyte (however, this layer at the interface has not been observed). Similarly, Y could likely diffuse to the LYCB surface, creating a Y-rich electronic conductive layer, including the presence of LiCl and LiBr which ensure Li conduction. Furthermore, Li halides are known to stabilize the Li/electrolyte interface. Liu et al. [57] report that the presence of LiBr in the SEI of liquid cells improves the cycling stability of symmetric cells during ST/PT as well as the rate capability and long-term cycling of full cells thanks to its high interface energy and low diffusion barrier preventing the growth of dendrites. Similar results have been observed with the presence of LiCl in the SEI [58,59]. Additionally, better cycling performances are obtained when LiBr is located in the SEI at the interface between Li and a sulfide solid electrolyte [60,61]. The IELI might act as a protective barrier for LYCB during cycling, as it occurs when fluorine is used to create a LiF-based SEI. Its thickness might depend on the electrolyte dimension.

Overall, our investigation reveals the complexity of the dynamics of the LYCB/Li interface, with the formation of the IELI as schematically illustrated in Fig. 7. Similar to other halides, LYCB chemically reacts with Li metal leading to the formation of LiCl, LiBr, and Y, as observed by AIMD, XRD, and NMR, causing the increase of the overpotential, the electronic conductivity, and a decrease of the ionic conductivity during ST/PT. This Y diffusion results in the formation of a layer poor in Y but rich in LiCl and LiBr, which is electronically insulating. The association of the Y-rich layer with the LiCl- and LiBr-rich layer creates the IELI. The larger presence of ionic species in this layer may prevent the supply of electrons from Li to LYCB, which stops the reduction reaction occurring between these two elements to go further, avoiding the total consumption of either the electrode or the electrolyte. As the IELI is created, the ionic and electronic conductivities of the cell become constant (see Fig. 3c). The formation of a dynamic interface while cycling improves the contact between Li and LYCB, thus decreasing the interfacial resistance and the overpotential of the cell until the latter stabilizes. Further analyses are necessary to understand the exact nature of the elements composing their role in the long cycling ability of the symmetric cell.

4. Conclusion

Our investigation sheds light into the intricate dynamics governing

the LYCB/Li interface during the cycling. Despite LYCB shows a high ionic conductivity (1.8 mS cm^{-1} at 25°C), there is an inherent instability with Li metal as demonstrated from experiments, AIMD simulations, and witnessed by the increase of the overpotential and the electronic conductivity at the beginning of the stripping/plating cycling. Post-mortem analysis unveils the formation of reaction products (LiCl, LiBr, and Y) that should decrease the cycling performance. Contrary to all predictions, the symmetric cells were able to perform over 1000 h at a capacity of 0.5 mAh cm^{-2} and a current density of 0.1 mA cm^{-2} without Li dendrites propagation. The outstanding cycling properties of LYCB are attributed to the formation of a dynamic ionic-electronic layered interface consisting of an electronic conductive and an ionic conductive layer, initiated by the reduction of LYCB, providing thermodynamic stability with Li metal. “Further decrease of the current SEI thickness (approximately $20 \mu\text{m}$) by using a thinner solid electrolyte and Li electrode might be necessary to ensure high-energy density cells”. However, the formation of this robust and favorable SEI presents a promising pathway toward the fabrication of solid-state batteries using halide electrolyte without the need for alternative anode.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Pierre Lannelongue: Writing – review & editing, Writing – original draft, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Simon Lindberg:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Elena Gonzalo:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology. **Andrey Golov:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Francisco Bonilla:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Juan Miguel Lopez del Amo:** Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Thomas Marchandier:** Writing – review & editing, Resources. **Artur Tron:** Writing – review & editing. **Javier Carrasco:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Pedro López-Aranguren:** .

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests:

Pedro Lopez Aranguren reports financial support was provided by European Commission. Pedro Lopez Aranguren has patent Process of treatment of a solid electrolyte material pending to 2,024,115-EP-EPA. If there are other authors, they declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Supplementary materials

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References

- H. Wu, H. Han, Z. Yan, Q. Zhao, J. Chen, Chloride solid-state electrolytes for all-solid-state lithium batteries, *J. Solid State Electrochem.* 26 (2022) 1791–1808, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10008-022-05230-x>.
- H. Kwak, S. Wang, J. Park, Y. Liu, K.T. Kim, Y. Choi, Y. Mo, Y.S. Jung, Emerging halide superionic conductors for all-solid-state batteries: design, synthesis, and practical applications, *ACS Energy Lett.* 7 (2022) 1776–1805, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.2c00438>.
- X. Li, J. Liang, X. Yang, K.R. Adair, C. Wang, F. Zhao, X. Sun, Progress and perspectives on halide lithium conductors for all-solid-state lithium batteries, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 13 (2020) 1429–1461, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EE03828K>.
- K. Tuo, C. Sun, S. Liu, Recent progress in and perspectives on emerging halide superionic conductors for all-solid-state batteries, *Electrochem. Energy Rev.* 6 (2023) 17, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s41918-023-00179-5>.
- W. Weppner, R.A. Huggins, Ionic conductivity of alkali metal chloroaluminate, *Phys. Lett. A* 58 (1976) 245–248, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-9601\(76\)90087-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0375-9601(76)90087-6).
- T. Asano, A. Sakai, S. Ouchi, M. Sakaida, A. Miyazaki, S. Hasegawa, Solid halide electrolytes with high lithium-ion conductivity for application in 4 V class bulk-type all-solid-state batteries, *Adv. Mater.* 30 (2018) 1803075, <https://doi.org/10.1002/adma.201803075>.
- L. Zhou, T.-T. Zuo, C.Y. Kwok, S.Y. Kim, A. Assoud, Q. Zhang, J. Janek, L.F. Nazar, High areal capacity, long cycle life 4 V ceramic all-solid-state Li-ion batteries enabled by chloride solid electrolytes, *Nat. Energy* 7 (2022) 83–93, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41560-021-00952-0>.
- L. Meabe, I. Aldalur, S. Lindberg, M. Arrese-Igor, M. Armand, M. Martínez-Ibañez, H. Zhang, Solid-state electrolytes for safe rechargeable lithium metal batteries: a strategic view, *Mater. Futur.* 2 (2023) 033501, <https://doi.org/10.1088/2752-5724/acdf3>.
- K.-H. Park, K. Kaup, A. Assoud, Q. Zhang, X. Wu, L.F. Nazar, High-voltage superionic halide solid electrolytes for all-solid-state Li-ion batteries, *ACS Energy Lett.* 5 (2020) 533–539, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.9b02599>.
- Z. Liu, S. Ma, J. Liu, S. Xiong, Y. Ma, H. Chen, High ionic conductivity achieved in Li₃Y(Br₃Cl₃) mixed halide solid electrolyte via promoted diffusion pathways and enhanced grain boundary, *ACS Energy Lett.* 6 (2021) 298–304, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.0c01690>.
- E. van der Maas, W. Zhao, Z. Cheng, T. Famprikis, M. Thijs, S.R. Parnell, S. Ganapathy, M. Wagemaker, Investigation of structure, ionic conductivity, and electrochemical stability of halogen substitution in solid-state ion conductor Li₃YBr_xCl_{6-x}, *J. Phys. Chem. C* 127 (2023) 125–132, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.jpcc.2c07910>.
- X. Nie, J. Hu, C. Li, Halide-based solid electrolytes: the history, progress, and challenges, *Interdiscip. Mater.* 2 (2023) 365–389, <https://doi.org/10.1002/idm2.12090>.
- Y. Fu, C. Ma, Interplay between Li₃YX₆ (X = Cl or Br) solid electrolytes and the Li metal anode, *Sci. China Mater.* 64 (2021) 1378–1385, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s40843-020-1580-3>.
- L.M. Riegger, R. Schlem, J. Sann, W.G. Zeier, J. Janek, Lithium-metal anode instability of the superionic halide solid electrolytes and the implications for solid-state batteries, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 60 (2021) 6718–6723, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.202015238>.
- Q. Wu, S. Xiong, F. Li, A. Matic, Electro-chemo-mechanical failure mechanisms of solid-state electrolytes, *Batter* (2023) e202300321, <https://doi.org/10.1002/batt.202300321>. Supercaps n/a.
- K. Wang, Q. Ren, Z. Gu, C. Duan, J. Wang, F. Zhu, Y. Fu, J. Hao, J. Zhu, L. He, C.-W. Wang, Y. Lu, J. Ma, C. Ma, A cost-effective and humidity-tolerant chloride solid electrolyte for lithium batteries, *Nat. Commun.* 12 (2021) 4410, <https://doi.org/10.1038/s41467-021-24697-2>.
- T. Yu, J. Liang, L. Luo, L. Wang, F. Zhao, G. Xu, X. Bai, R. Yang, S. Zhao, J. Wang, J. Yu, X. Sun, Superionic fluorinated halide solid electrolytes for highly stable Li-metal in all-solid-state Li batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (2021) 2101915, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202101915>.
- C. Yu, Y. Li, K.R. Adair, W. Li, K. Goubitz, Y. Zhao, M.J. Willans, M.A. Thijs, C. Wang, F. Zhao, Q. Sun, S. Deng, J. Liang, X. Li, R. Li, T.-K. Sham, H. Huang, S. Lu, S. Zhao, L. Zhang, L. van Eijck, Y. Huang, X. Sun, Tuning ionic conductivity and electrode compatibility of Li₃YBr₆ for high-performance all solid-state Li batteries, *Nano Energy* 77 (2020) 105097, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.nanoen.2020.105097>.
- P. Ganesan, M. Soans, M.A. Cambaz, R. Zimmermanns, R. Gond, S. Fuchs, Y. Hu, S. Baumgart, M. Sotoudeh, D. Stepien, H. Stein, A. Groß, D. Bresser, A. Varzi, M. Fichtner, Fluorine-substituted halide solid electrolytes with enhanced stability toward the lithium metal, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 15 (2023) 38391–38402, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmi.3c03513>.
- X. Luo, X. He, H. Su, Y. Zhong, X. Wang, J. Tu, Effective regulation towards electrochemical stability of superionic solid electrolyte via facile dual-halogen strategy, *Chem. Eng. J.* 465 (2023) 143036, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2023.143036>.
- C. Wang, J. Liang, J. Luo, J. Liu, X. Li, F. Zhao, R. Li, H. Huang, S. Zhao, L. Zhang, J. Wang, X. Sun, A universal wet-chemistry synthesis of solid-state halide electrolytes for all-solid-state lithium-metal batteries, *Sci. Adv.* 7 (2021) eabh1896, <https://doi.org/10.1126/sciadv.abh1896>.
- J. Peng, L. Xian, L.-B. Kong, Effects of Br substitution to improve the ionic conductivity of chloride electrolytes without changing crystal structure, *Ionics (Kiel)* 29 (2023) 2657–2664, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11581-023-05028-5>.
- J. Liang, X. Li, S. Wang, K.R. Adair, W. Li, Y. Zhao, C. Wang, Y. Hu, L. Zhang, S. Zhao, S. Lu, H. Huang, R. Li, Y. Mo, X. Sun, Site-occupation-tuned superionic Li₃ScCl_{3+x} halide solid electrolytes for all-solid-state batteries, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.* 142 (2020) 7012–7022, <https://doi.org/10.1021/jacs.0c00134>.
- J. Liang, E. van der Maas, J. Luo, X. Li, N. Chen, K.R. Adair, W. Li, J. Li, Y. Hu, J. Liu, L. Zhang, S. Zhao, S. Lu, J. Wang, H. Huang, W. Zhao, S. Parnell, R.I. Smith, S. Ganapathy, M. Wagemaker, X. Sun, A series of ternary metal chloride superionic conductors for high-performance all-solid-state lithium batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 12 (2022) 2103921, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202103921>.
- S. Wang, Q. Bai, A.M. Nolan, Y. Liu, S. Gong, Q. Sun, Y. Mo, Lithium chlorides and bromides as promising solid-state chemistries for fast ion conductors with good electrochemical stability, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 58 (2019) 8039–8043, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201901938>.
- A.L. Santhosha, L. Medenbach, J.R. Buchheim, P. Adelhelm, The indium–lithium electrode in solid-state lithium-ion batteries: phase formation, redox potentials, and interface stability, *Batter. Supercaps* 2 (2019) 524–529, <https://doi.org/10.1002/batt.201800149>.
- L. Guo, J. Zheng, L. Zhao, Y. Yao, Interfacial instabilities in halide-based solid-state batteries, *MRS Bull.* (2023), <https://doi.org/10.1557/s43577-023-00607-3>.
- H. Kwak, D. Han, J. Lyoo, J. Park, S.H. Jung, Y. Han, G. Kwon, H. Kim, S.-T. Hong, K.-W. Nam, Y.S. Jung, New cost-effective halide solid electrolytes for all-solid-state batteries: mechanochemically prepared Fe³⁺-substituted Li₂ZrCl₆, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (2021) 2003190, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202003190>.
- T. Yu, L. Wang, Q. Sun, B. Xiao, X. Bai, R. Yang, Y. Duan, Y. Wu, G. Li, G. Xu, S. Zhao, L. Wang, J. Yu, J. Wang, Enabling high ionic conductivity in yttrium-based lithium halide electrolytes by composition modulation for all-solid-state batteries, *Mater. Today Chem.* 30 (2023) 101510, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.mtchem.2023.101510>.
- K. Wang, Q. Ye, J. Zhang, H. Huang, Y. Gan, X. He, W. Zhang, Halide electrolyte Li₃InCl₆-based all-solid-state lithium batteries with slurry-coated LiNi_{0.8}Co_{0.1}Mn_{0.1}O₂ composite cathode: effect of binders, *Front. Mater.* 8 (2021), <https://doi.org/10.3389/fmats.2021.727617>.
- W. Ji, D. Zheng, X. Zhang, T. Ding, D. Qu, A kinetically stable anode interface for Li₃YCl₆-based all-solid-state lithium batteries, *J. Mater. Chem. A* 9 (2021) 15012–15018, <https://doi.org/10.1039/D1TA03042F>.
- S.Y. Kim, K. Kaup, K.-H. Park, A. Assoud, L. Zhou, J. Liu, X. Wu, L.F. Nazar, Lithium ytterbium-based halide solid electrolytes for high voltage all-solid-state batteries, *ACS Mater. Lett.* 3 (2021) 930–938, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmaterialslett.1c00142>.
- X. Li, J. Liang, N. Chen, J. Luo, K.R. Adair, C. Wang, M.N. Banis, T.-K. Sham, L. Zhang, S. Zhao, S. Lu, H. Huang, R. Li, X. Sun, Water-mediated synthesis of a superionic halide solid electrolyte, *Angew. Chem. Int. Ed.* 58 (2019) 16427–16432, <https://doi.org/10.1002/anie.201909805>.
- T. Cheng, B.V. Merinov, S. Morozov, W.A.I. Goddard, Quantum mechanics reactive dynamics study of solid Li-electrode/Li₆PS₄Cl-electrolyte interface, *ACS Energy Lett.* 2 (2017) 1454–1459, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsenergylett.7b00319>.
- S. Wenzel, S.J. Sedlmaier, C. Dietrich, W.G. Zeier, J. Janek, Interfacial reactivity and interphase growth of argyrodite solid electrolytes at lithium metal electrodes, *Solid State Ion. Gener. Batter.* 318 (2018) 102–112, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ssi.2017.07.005>.
- C. Rosenbach, F. Walther, J. Ruhl, M. Hartmann, T.A. Hendriks, S. Ohno, J. Janek, W.G. Zeier, Visualizing the chemical incompatibility of halide and sulfide-based electrolytes in solid-state batteries, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 13 (2023) 2203673, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202203673>.
- K. Tuo, F. Yin, F. Mi, C. Sun, Elucidating the diffusion pathway of lithium ions in superionic halide solid electrolytes Li_{2-x}Hf_{1-x}In_xCl₆ for all-solid-state lithium-metal based batteries, *J. Energy Chem.* 87 (2023) 12–23, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jechem.2023.08.016>.
- S. Zhang, F. Zhao, S. Wang, J. Liang, J. Wang, C. Wang, H. Zhang, K. Adair, W. Li, M. Li, H. Duan, Y. Zhao, R. Yu, R. Li, H. Huang, L. Zhang, S. Zhao, S. Lu, T.-K. Sham, Y. Mo, X. Sun, Advanced high-voltage all-solid-state Li-ion batteries enabled by a dual-halogen solid electrolyte, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 11 (2021) 2100836, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202100836>.
- W. Tang, W. Xia, F. Hussain, J. Zhu, S. Han, W. Yin, P. Yu, J. Lei, D.S. Butenko, L. Wang, Y. Zhao, A dual-halogen electrolyte for protective-layer-free all-solid-state lithium batteries, *J. Power Sources* 568 (2023) 232992, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2023.232992>.
- Y. Zhang, C. Sun, Composite lithium protective layer formed in situ for stable lithium metal batteries, *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces* 13 (2021) 12099–12105, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acsmi.1c00745>.

- [41] X. Li, J. Liang, J. Luo, M. Norouzi Banis, C. Wang, W. Li, S. Deng, C. Yu, F. Zhao, Y. Hu, T.-K. Sham, L. Zhang, S. Zhao, S. Lu, H. Huang, R. Li, K.R. Adair, X. Sun, Air-stable Li_3InCl_6 electrolyte with high voltage compatibility for all-solid-state batteries, *Energy Environ. Sci.* 12 (2019) 2665–2671, <https://doi.org/10.1039/C9EE02311A>.
- [42] Q. Wang, X. Ma, Q. Liu, D. Sun, X. Zhou, Fluorine-doped Li_3InCl_6 to enhance ionic conductivity and air stability, *J. Alloys Compd.* 969 (2023) 172479, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jallcom.2023.172479>.
- [43] A. Zur, T.C. McGill, Lattice match: an application to heteroepitaxy, *J. Appl. Phys.* 55 (1984) 378–386, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.333084>.
- [44] K. Okhotnikov, T. Charpentier, S. Cadars, Supercell program: a combinatorial structure-generation approach for the local-level modeling of atomic substitutions and partial occupancies in crystals, *J. Cheminform.* 8 (2016) 17, <https://doi.org/10.1186/s13321-016-0129-3>.
- [45] A. Jain, S.P. Ong, G. Hautier, W. Chen, W.D. Richards, S. Dacek, S. Cholia, D. Gunter, D. Skinner, G. Ceder, K.A. Persson, Commentary: the materials project: a materials genome approach to accelerating materials innovation, *APL Mater.* 1 (2013) 011002, <https://doi.org/10.1063/1.4812323>.
- [46] G. Kresse, J. Hafner, Ab initio molecular dynamics for liquid metals, *Phys. Rev. B* 47 (1993) 558–561, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.47.558>.
- [47] G. Kresse, J. Furthmüller, Efficiency of ab-initio total energy calculations for metals and semiconductors using a plane-wave basis set, *Comput. Mater. Sci.* 6 (1996) 15–50, [https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-0256\(96\)00008-0](https://doi.org/10.1016/0927-0256(96)00008-0).
- [48] G. Kresse, J. Furthmüller, Efficient iterative schemes for ab initio total-energy calculations using a plane-wave basis set, *Phys. Rev. B* 54 (1996) 11169–11186, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.54.11169>.
- [49] J.P. Perdew, K. Burke, M. Ernzerhof, Generalized gradient approximation made simple, *Phys. Rev. Lett.* 77 (1996) 3865–3868, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevLett.77.3865>.
- [50] P.E. Blöchl, Projector augmented-wave method, *Phys. Rev. B* 50 (1994) 17953–17979, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.50.17953>.
- [51] G. Kresse, D. Joubert, From ultrasoft pseudopotentials to the projector augmented-wave method, *Phys. Rev. B* 59 (1999) 1758–1775, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.59.1758>.
- [52] H.J. Monkhorst, J.D. Pack, Special points for Brillouin-zone integrations, *Phys. Rev. B* 13 (1976) 5188–5192, <https://doi.org/10.1103/PhysRevB.13.5188>.
- [53] D.J. Evans, B.L. Holian, The Nose–Hoover thermostat, *J. Chem. Phys.* 83 (1985) 4069–4074, <https://api.semanticscholar.org/CorpusID:94786326>.
- [54] W. Tang, E. Sanville, G. Henkelman, A grid-based Bader analysis algorithm without lattice bias, *J. Phys. Condens. Matter* 21 (2009) 084204, <https://doi.org/10.1088/0953-8984/21/8/084204>.
- [55] B. Shao, Y. Huang, F. Han, Electronic conductivity of lithium solid electrolytes, *Adv. Energy Mater.* 13 (2023) 2204098, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202204098>.
- [56] Y. Ren, J. Liu, C. Zhang, H. Zhuang, C. Sun, G. Cai, X. Tan, S. Sun, First-principles study of a stable anode interface based on the electron tunneling effect to suppress transition metal reduction in lithium halide solid-state electrolytes, *Chem. Eng. J. Adv.* 12 (2022) 100377, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2022.100377>.
- [57] P. Liu, H. Su, Y. Liu, Y. Zhong, C. Xian, Y. Zhang, X. Wang, X. Xia, J. Tu, LiBr–LiF-rich solid–electrolyte interface layer on lithiophilic 3D framework for enhanced lithium metal anode, *Small Struct.* 3 (2022) 2200010, <https://doi.org/10.1002/ssr.202200010>.
- [58] J. Lu, X. Fu, K. Shi, Y. Xu, D. Dang, Y. Min, Q. Liu, Y. Zheng, In situ construction of a LiF/LiCl-rich solid electrolyte interphase for lithium ion unimpeded transport, *Ind. Eng. Chem. Res.* 63 (2024) 6249–6256, <https://doi.org/10.1021/acs.iecr.3c04375>.
- [59] Z. Lin, F. Bettels, T. Li, S.K. Satheesh, Y. Liu, C. Zhang, F. Ding, L. Zhang, Constructing LiCl-rich solid electrolyte interphase by high amine-containing 1,2,4,5-benzenetetramine tetrahydrochloride additive, *Adv. Electron. Mater.* 10 (2024) 2300772, <https://doi.org/10.1002/aenm.202300772>.
- [60] B. Zhao, Y. Shi, J. Wu, C. Xing, Y. Liu, W. Ma, X. Liu, Y. Jiang, J. Zhang, Stabilizing $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ /lithium metal anode interface by in-situ bifunctional composite layer, *Chem. Eng. J.* 429 (2022) 132411, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cej.2021.132411>.
- [61] B. Zhao, J. Wu, Z. Wang, W. Ma, Y. Shi, Y. Jiang, J. Jiang, X. Liu, Y. Xu, J. Zhang, Incorporation of lithium halogen in $\text{Li}_7\text{P}_3\text{S}_{11}$ glass-ceramic and the interface improvement mechanism, *Electrochim. Acta* 390 (2021) 138849, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.electacta.2021.138849>.